

The prognostic value of cardiac biomarkers in predicting cardiovascular outcomes

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

Created by

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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

We will collect quantitative data from electronic health records and blood samples held at the National Safe Haven. Pseudonymised blood samples, taken at the time of each patient's first transplant assessment, will be re-analysed for cardiac biomarkers of interest. The final data volume, comprising approximately 2,200 patients and including administrative and general data, will be up to 100 GB.

II. Standards and metadata

All data will be collected, managed and stored in compliance with the requirements of the Joint Code of Practice for Research, BBSRC's Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice and the National Safe Haven security standards. Data collection and generation standards will be set by the National Safe Haven teams. Only anonymised and aggregated data will leave the National Safe Haven and will be stored on a local networked data storage. Data released for sharing will be validated and verified in line with accepted best practices. Data will be accompanied by the contextual information or documentation (metadata) needed to all necessary details on the origin and manipulation of the data to a secondary user, in order to prevent any misuse, misinterpretation or confusion. The Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) (cdisc.org/standards) will be adopted.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Data created in this project are not yet publicly available; however, this project will use existing datasets and blood samples from patients stored in the Scottish National Safe Haven (NSH).

IV. Secondary use

Sharing our data and files will enable other researchers to conduct further analyses and may answer questions beyond their original purpose.

V. Methods for data sharing

The Trusted Research Environment (TRE) datasets, which contain public health records, cannot be shared. However, summary-level and newly created data will be available in an open-access repository unless they are sensitive or subject to embargo. The repositories will provide a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and suggest citations for future references.

VI. Proprietary data

We reserve the right to retain unpublished data within the group until sufficient repeats and validations have been conducted for its meaningful analysis and publication.

VII. Timeframes

The data will be archived and made available for sharing, but will be embargoed until one year after the publication of the main study papers. Until then, the study team will have exclusive use of the data.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

The data will be stored in non-specialist file formats, such as .txt, .csv, and .xls, to facilitate sharing and ensure long-term accessibility of the data.